

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL RATIOS -INDIAN PUBLIC NON-LIFE INSURANCE SECTOR

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Performance evaluation is an art through which one can learn about the efficiency achieved in the working of a particular organization. As regards performance evaluation of an organization, there are various measures to analyze performance of any organization. These measures are broadly classified into two categories namely, financial and non-financial factors. Among financial factors, the most important is Financial Ratios. Analysis through ratios is compared to Doctor' kit for diagnosing the performance of the firm. It is the evaluation of a firms' prospect for survival and growth. An analyst should develop the skill of identifying red flags. They should be used only to evaluate the performance of the firm as a whole. They, by themselves do not provide any insight into the performance of the firm.

As per the World Insurance Report, published by the reinsurance major "Swiss Re" the premium in non-life insurance business grew by 1.9 per cent. Latin America reported remarkably high growth. The Report mentions that the year 2011 witnessed exceptionally high catastrophe losses in Japan, Australia, and the United States, while European countries generally enjoyed low catastrophe claims. In 2011, total economic losses to Society due to disasters (both insured and uninsured) reached an estimated USD 370 billion, compared to USD 226 billion in 2010. The earthquake in Japan, the country's worst on record in terms of

magnitude, alone accounted for 57 percent of global economic losses. The insured losses from natural catastrophes appeared to be to the tune of USD 110 billion.

As at end-September 2012, there are fifty-two insurance companies operating in India; of which twenty-four are in the life insurance business and twenty-seven are in non-life insurance business. Of the fifty two companies presently in operations, eight are in the public sector - two are specialized insurers, namely ECGC and AIC, one in life insurance namely LIC, four in general insurance.

The public sector insurers exhibited growth in 2011-12 at 21.50 per cent; as against the previous year's growth rate of 21.84 percent. The private sector general insurers registered a growth of 28.06 per cent, which is higher than 24.67 percent achieved during the previous year.

Methodology:

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, secondary data is used. The main secondary data includes annual report of Insurance Regulatory Development Authority, Department of Economic Affairs in the Ministry of Finance, Business world, Business Today. Apart from publications, number of websites is also accessed to gather the information for the study. Selected 111 private companies from whole sale & retail trade and 64 private compare from Real Estate sectors are chosen for the analysis. Data from IRDA Bulletin for the last six years from 2006-07 to 2011-12 is made available. To analyse the data, financial ratios as well as descriptive statistics are used. The descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and coefficient of variation.

Objective of the study is:

To study financial ratios of Indian public Non-life Insurance sector

Scope of the study:

This study covers only Indian public non-life Insurance Sector. It includes General Insurance Business covering National Insurance Co. Ltd., New India Assurances Co. Ltd., Oriental Insurance Co. Ltd. and United India Insurance Co. Ltd. This provides, inter alia, a brief analysis by size and industry.

Findings:

1. RONW, ROTA and ROI of public non-life Insurance sector gradually decrease except last year during the study period with average of 0.096, 0.017 and 0.036 respectively.
2. Dividend payout ratio fluctuates sharply with standard deviation of 0.177 and mean of 0.143.
3. Current Ratio/Short Term Solvency position of public non-financial Insurance sector is more or less constant with Coefficient of Variation of 0.088 and average of 0.465.
4. Commission Expense Ratio has been reducing at snail's pace during the study period with an average of 0.083.
5. Operating Expense Ratio has highly consistent with Coefficient of Variation of 0.069 and an average of 0.229 over the study period.
6. Claims incurred ratio is an average of 84.802 percent of Net Earned Premium with Standard Deviation of 8.974
7. Investment income ratio oscillates during the study period with an average and Standard Deviation of 0.492 and 0.289 respectively.
8. Net earnings ratio more or less, decreases during the study period with an average and standard deviation of 0.133 and 0.148 respectively.

Conclusion:

In nut shell, Financial Ratios cannot lead to appropriate managerial actions for maintaining or improving the performance. They, at best guide one to the right questions. Therefore, managers usually use financial ratios to understand economic consequences of their decisions. For much more meaningful analysis, they should be used in conjunction with non-financial ratios or other non-financial measures of performance in different activities of the firm. This study undoubtedly helps in highlighting the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, opportunities and threat of the organization. This is immensely useful for the investors to know survival and competence of sectors.

References:

1. "Finances of Non-government and Non-financial Private Limited Companies: 2010-11" RBI Monthly Bulletin 2012, October, Pp 1895-1928.
2. "Finances of Private Limited Companies, 2007-08" RBI Monthly Bulletin 2009, October, Pp 1895-1928.
3. Dr. Jeelan Basha.V, "FDI Companies-A review" The Management Accountant, June, 2012, Pp- 665-66.
4. <http://www.irda.gov.in>

Appendix-1. Financial Ratios of Public Non-life Insurance Sector

Financial Ratios	2011-12	2010-11	2009-10	2008-09	2007-08	2006-07
1. RONW	0.071	-0.011	0.086	0.030	0.160	0.241
2. ROTA	0.011	-0.002	0.014	0.006	0.028	0.043
3. ROI	0.023	0.000	0.030	0.019	0.059	0.083
4. D/P Ratio	0.102	-0.186	0.210	0.330	0.204	0.200
5. Current Ratio	0.447	0.445	0.526	0.507	0.442	0.424
6. Commission Exp. Ratio	0.074	0.074	0.084	0.087	0.088	0.093
7. Operating Expense Ratio	0.215	0.253	0.241	0.228	0.211	0.226
8. Claims Incurred Ratio	89.22	97.030	88.270	76.840	72.230	85.220
9. Investment Income Ratio	0.298	0.388	0.374	0.321	1.062	0.506
10. Net Earnings Ratio	0.046	-0.008	0.076	0.054	0.375	0.254

Appendix-2. Statistical Description of Public Non-life Insurance Sector

Financial Ratios	Sum	Average	S.D	C.V.	Skew	Kurt
1. RONW	0.577	0.096	0.091	0.949	0.695	-0.116
2. ROTA	0.1	0.017	0.016	0.976	0.822	0.074
3. ROI	0.214	0.036	0.030	0.844	0.733	-0.241
4. D/P Ratio	0.86	0.143	0.177	1.234	-1.551	3.074
5. Current Ratio	2.791	0.465	0.041	0.088	0.877	-1.264
6. Commission Exp. Ratio	0.5	0.083	0.008	0.093	-0.363	-1.578
7. Operating Expense Ratio	1.374	0.229	0.016	0.069	0.527	-0.695
8. Claims Incurred Ratio	508.81	84.802	8.974	0.106	-0.222	-0.651
9. Investment Income Ratio	2.949	0.492	0.289	0.587	2.129	4.683
10. Net Earnings Ratio	0.797	0.133	0.148	1.117	1.088	-0.258